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NEW FINDINGS ON PROTECTED AND STRICTLY PROTECTED SPECIES CONFIRM THE VALUE OF THE PRIME HOVERFLY AREA NETWORK

ABSTRACT: With environmental pressures on the rise, the establishment of protected areas is a key strategy for preserving biodiversity. The fact that many species are losing their battle against extinction despite being within protected areas raises the question of their effectiveness. The aim of this study was to evaluate established Priority Hoverfly Areas (PHAs) and areas that are not yet but could potentially be included in the PHA network, using data from new field surveys. Additionally, species distribution models have been created for two new species recognized as important and added to the list of key hoverfly species. Maps of potential distribution of these species were superimposed on maps of protected areas and PHAs to quantify percentages of overlap. The results of this study are not statistically significant, which could be influenced by a small sample size. However, the results of species distribution models and the extent of overlap with PHAs confirm the utility of these expert-generated designations.

KEYWORDS: Hoverflies, Prime Hoverfly Areas, evaluation, conservation

INTRODUCTION

Biodiversity is under immense anthropogenic pressure globally, with the increasing number of natural habitats being converted to agricultural land or urban areas every day. Establishment of protected areas (PA) is probably the most common strategy for nature conservation (Groom et al., 2006; Primack, 2008). An important role of PAs is preserving natural habitats (Bruner et al., 2001; Chape et al., 2005), maintaining existing populations, as well as reducing species extinction risks, especially in the light of growing concern of climate

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change. However, many species are losing the battle with extinction, despite being within PAs, mostly due to poor management and only partial overlap of their distribution with PAs, which is a big issue especially for many invertebrate groups. Additionally, protected areas are sometimes established for political or economical reasons, rather than based on ecological principles (Kati et al., 2004). Thus, it is of great relevance to evaluate their effectiveness.

Important areas for many biotic groups have been identified, using different approaches for site choice, in order to strengthen conservation efforts and to encourage better protected area designations (Vujić et al., 2016). However, most efforts have been focused on well-known species, leaving most invertebrate groups under-represented.

Insects have enormous functional significance because of the large number of individuals and their great intra- and interspecific variability. Additionally, insect pollinators play an important ecological and economic role but, despite this fact, they are still receiving a disproportionately small amount of attention.

Hoverflies are a diverse insect group that play many important roles in ecosystems. The widespread distribution of hoverflies, the availability of excellent taxonomic keys for species identification (particularly for European species), and differences in the environmental requirements of larvae are features that make Syrphidae potentially good bioindicators (Sommaggio, 1999). Hoverflies are recognized as the second most important pollinator group after bees (Larson et al., 2001). Moreover, they function in the decomposition of various materials, adults represent an important part of the diets of many species, and larvae can be used as biological control agents.

At European level, some hoverfly species have been recognized as threatened and some of them have been listed in the national Red Lists (Jentzsch, 1998; Ssymank and Doczkal, 1998; Stuke et al., 1998; Doczkal et al., 1999; Cederberg et al., 2010; Ssymank et al., 2011). Additional efforts are needed in order to take the conservation of hoverflies to a higher level, since they are still completely absent from international lists such as IUCN Red List, or legal instruments such as Annexes of the EU Habitats Directive.

In Serbia, 77 hoverfly species have been protected by national law *Code of Regulations on the Declaration and Protection of Strictly Protected and Protected Wild Species of Plants, Animals and Fungi* (Official Gazette of RS, No. 5/2010). In order to improve the status of hoverflies, based on long-term monitoring data, Vujić et al. (2016) identified species of conservation interest and proposed priority areas for their conservation in Serbia. The selection process relied on expert opinion and it was part of an ongoing national project (Conservation strategy for the preservation of protected and strictly protected hoverflies [Diptera: Syrphidae] in Serbia).

The aim of this study was to evaluate the established Prime Hoverfly Areas (PHAs) and areas that are not included in the PHA network but could be potentially added, using data from new field surveys. Additionally, species distribution models were created for two new species recognized as important and added to the list of key hoverfly species.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Specimens were collected from April to September, over a two year period (2016–2017). Localities were surveyed by transect walks. Hoverflies were identified to species level.

In order to evaluate established Prime Hoverfly Areas (PHAs) and potential new ones, data on key hoverfly species was extracted from a database hosted by the Department of Biology and Ecology, Faculty of Sciences, Novi Sad, Serbia. Species distribution models (SDMs), previously reported in Vujić et al. (2016), were consulted to determine if these key species had been predicted to occur in the sampled localities. Students *t* tests were conducted to test the predictive power of SDMs. Statistical analysis was performed using the R statistical platform (version 3.3.1, R Core Team, 2016).

Species distribution data for selected species occurring in Serbia were extracted from the database of the Department for Biology and Ecology, University of Novi Sad. Occurrence points for species that will be suggested for protection are mainly the result of systematic field collecting in the period 2016–2017. In order to reduce bias caused by oversampling in some areas, a species occurrence record thinning procedure was applied using the ‘thin’ function within the R package *red* (Cardoso, 2017) (R Development Core Team, 2016). Only species that met the criteria for being suggested for protection and with more than five different occurrence points after the thinning procedure were selected, which resulted in only two species for which it was possible to build the models. The *dismo* R package (Hijmans et al., 2016) for Maximum Entropy Modelling (Maxent) was used for conducting species distribution modelling. For preliminary model building 19 bioclimatic variables plus elevation data were used (30 arc-second resolution), generated for each locality based on the WorldClim dataset (Hijmans et al., 2005). First run was made with all variables for separate species. In the second step, the modelling procedure using only variables with contribution above 10% in the initial model was performed. A map showing the potential current distribution was created for each species. True skill statistic (TSS) as a measure of model accuracy was used (ranging from -1 to +1, where +1 indicates perfect agreement, while values of zero or less indicate a model performance not better than random) (Allouche et al., 2006).

To assess the efficiency of Protected Areas and Prime Hoverfly Areas, we overlapped the projected species distribution maps of two new key species with a map of The World Database of Protected Areas (<http://www.wdpa.org>) and map of Prime Hoverfly Areas. Only protected areas of IUCN categories I–VI were considered. We calculated the percentage of a projected species range that overlapped with nationally protected areas (PA) and Prime Hoverfly Areas (PHA). All analyses were carried out with ArcGIS vs. 10.1.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A total of 44 key hoverfly species were assessed across 28 localities in Serbia (Table 1). Fifteen of these species were found in each of the localities in which they were predicted to occur by SDMs, four species were found in most of the SDM-predicted localities, three occurred in just a few of their predicted localities, and 19 were not found in any of their predicted localities. *Chrysotoxum montanum* Nedeljković & Vujić, 2015, *C. orthostylum* Vujić, 2015, and *Merodon illiricus* in litt. were each found at five localities but, due to the lack of data, these species had not been modelled in SDMs, so it was impossible to draw further conclusions on the predictive power of their respective SDMs.

Table 1. List of key hoverfly species found in surveyed localities

Species	Locality
<i>Arctophila bombiformis</i> (Fallen, 1810)	Zlatar – Karaula; Ozren – towards Tičje Polje
<i>Arctophila superbieni</i> (Muller, 1776)	Zlatar – Drmanovići
<i>Blera fallax</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Golija – Odvrćenica 2
<i>Brachyopa maculipennis</i> Thompson, 1980	Stara Planina – Dojkinci 1
<i>Cheilosia bracusi</i> Vujić & Claussen, 1994	Dubašnica – Dubašnica 1 and 2; Stara Planina – Dojkinci 1 and 2
<i>Cheilosia carbonaria</i> Egger, 1860	Odvraćenica 2
<i>Cheilosia cumanica</i> (Szilady, 1938)	Dubašnica – Dubašnica 2, Demizlok; Malinik – Malinik, Zlot
<i>Cheilosia frontalis</i> Loew, 1857	Stara Planina – Dojkinci 2; Besna Kobila – Besna Kobila 2.1, 2.2 and 2.3
<i>Cheilosia griseifacies</i> Vujić, 1994	Vojvodina – Bezdán 2
<i>Cheilosia hypena</i> (Becker, 1894)	Dubašnica – Dubašnica 1, Lazar River gorge, Malinik – Malinik, Zlot; Besna Kobila – Kriva Feja
<i>Cheilosia insignis</i> Loew, 1857	Malinik – Malinik
<i>Cheilosia longula</i> (Zetterstedt, 1838)	Besna Kobila – Besna Kobila 1
<i>Cheilosia morio</i> (Zetterstedt, 1838)	Stara Planina – Dojkinci 1
<i>Cheilosia personata</i> Loew, 1857	Zlatar – Karaula, Panorama; Ozren – towards Tičje Polje; Stara Planina – Dojkinci 2
<i>Cheilosia redi</i> Vujić, 1996	Malinik – Zlot; Besna Kobila – Besna Kobila 1
<i>Cheilosia rhynchops</i> Egger, 1860	Stara Planina – Dojkinci 2
<i>Chrysotoxum montanum</i> Nedeljković & Vujić, 2015	Zlatar – Drmanovići; Golija – Čeka
<i>Chrysotoxum orthostylum</i> Vujić, 2015	Zlatar – Drmanovići, Karaula
<i>Chrysotoxum tomentosum</i> Giglio-Tos, 1890	Zlatar – Drmanovići, Panorama; Golija – Čeka

<i>Criorhina asilica</i> (Fallen, 1816)	Stara Planina
<i>Dasysyrphus lenensis</i> Bagatshanova, 1980	Dubašnica – Dubašnica 2; Golija – Odvračenica 2
<i>Dasysyrphus pauxilus</i> (Williston, 1887)	Dubašnica – Dubašnica 2
<i>Eumerus clavatus</i> Becker, 1923	Malinik – Zlot
<i>Eupeodes nielsenii</i> (Dusek & Láška, 1976)	Stara Planina – Dojkinci 2
<i>Merodon aerarius</i> Rondani, 1857	Zlatar – Drmanovići, Panorama; Prijepolje – Kamena Gora 1; Golija – Čeka, Odvračenica 1 and 2, Golijska Reka, Potok, Karalići, Toranj; Besna Kobila – Besna Kobila 1
<i>Merodon desaturinus</i> Vujic, Simic & Radenkovic, 1995	Stara Planina – Dojkinci 2
<i>Merodon illiricus</i> in litt.	Zlatar – Drmanovići, Panorama; Stara Planina – above Topli Do
<i>Merodon loewi</i> van der Goot, 1964	Malinik – Malinik, Zlot
<i>Merodon moesiacus</i> in litt.	Zlatar – Drmanovići, Panorama; Golija – Čeka, Odvračenica 1, Čeka, Golijska reka, Karalići, Toranj
<i>Merodon trebevicensis</i> Strobl, 1900	Golija – Čeka
<i>Myolepta potens</i> Harris, 1776	Besna Kobila – Besna Kobila 1
<i>Orthonevra montana</i> Vujić, 1999	Golija – Odvračenica 2
<i>Paragus finitimus</i> Goeldlin, 1971	Zlatar – Panorama
<i>Pelecocera tricincta</i> Meigen, 1822	Zlatibor – Zlatibor 1 and 2
<i>Pipizella bispina</i> Šimić, 1987	Golija – Karalići
<i>Pipizella zloti</i> Vujić, 1997	Dubašnica – Lazar River gorge; Malinik – Malinik
<i>Pocota personata</i> (Harris, 1780)	Malinik – Malinik
<i>Sericomyia lappona</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Golija – Odvračenica 1, Golijska Reka, Potok
<i>Sphagina sibirica</i> Stackelberg, 1953	Dubašnica – Dubašnica 1
<i>Temnostoma vespiforme</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Golija – Čeka
<i>Trichopsomyia flavitarsis</i> (Meigen, 1822)	Stara Planina – Dojkinci 2; Prijepolje – Kamena Gora 1
<i>Xylota florum</i> (Fabricius, 1805)	Golija – Odvračenica 1
<i>Xylota jakutorum</i> Bagachanova, 1980	Golija – Odvračenica 2
<i>Xylota tarda</i> Meigen, 1822	Dubašnica – Demizlok; Malinik – Malinik; Vojvodina – Bezdan

When it comes to testing the predictive power of SDMs, results of t test were not statistically significant ($t=0.6983$, $df=76.37$, $p=0.17$). However, this could be due to relatively small sample size. Another possible cause that could influence the structure of the sample is the fact that some species are simply more rare and therefore more difficult to find.

Figure 1. Maps of potential current distribution of species:
a) *C. tomentosum*, b) *M. moesiacus*

According to the models (Figure 1), the highest suitability for species *M. moesiacus* is on high peaks of mountains Tara, Golija, Kopaonik and Stara Planina, where the species was found previously, but also on the mountain Prokletije in southwestern part of Serbia. As far as *C. tomentosum* is concerned, most suitable areas for this species are the same as for *M. moesiacus*, with additional mountain peaks on Suva Planina and Besna Kobila in eastern part of Serbia being marked as suitable. Some areas identified as suitable and therefore important by the SDMs (e.g. mountains in the southern Serbia like Besna Kobila or Dukat) are not part of any PA or PHA. Additionally, findings of key hoverfly species in those areas, confirm their potential significance for survival of these species.

Maps of projected distribution for *Chrysotoxum tomentosum* and *Merodon moesiacus* were superimposed on maps of Protected Areas and Prime Hoverfly Areas in order to quantify the percentage of overlapping. Our results showed high percentage of overlapping with PHA network, while percentage of overlapping with PAs was significantly lower (Table 2), which could be interpreted as an additional confirmation of validity of expert generated network and, on the other hand, indicate the need for evaluation of Protected Areas in Serbia.

Table 2. Percentage of protected areas that overlapped with projected species distribution (%PASD) and Percentage of Prime Hoverfly Area that overlapped with projected species distribution (%PHAD)

Species	%PASD	%PHAD
M. moesiacus	20.45	92.03
C. tomentosum	14.91	93.11

Many rare and endangered species occur in areas that have some form of legal protection. Nevertheless, a decline in those species has been noted in many countries. Establishment of protected and/or prime areas for various species is an important step for species conservation. However, many studies have indicated the need for further assessments of such areas. For instance, the European Union's Natura 2000 network is one of the most important conservation efforts being implemented across Europe. Nonetheless, no comprehensive evaluation of the effectiveness of this network has been conducted (Maiorano et al., 2007), with only a few published studies on this topic, most of which are focused on plants (Dimitrakipoulos et al., 2007; Chiarucci et al., 2008) or vertebrates (Maiorano et al., 2007), meaning that invertebrates remain under-represented.

Climate change is another issue that needs to be addressed in assessing the effectiveness of protected areas and the creation and evaluation of management strategies. Species ranges cannot be considered static under environmental change (Klorvuttimontara et al., 2011), so protected areas and conservation networks must be properly designed to facilitate responses to those changes. While expert knowledge is fundamental, SDMs can aid in decision-making and the implementation of strategies to protect species, thus accounting for the uncertainty of future climate scenarios.

CONCLUSION

The results of this study confirm the validity of expert generated PHA network. While proper designation of such networks is of great importance, evaluation of their effectiveness is a part of the conservation process that is usually neglected.

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НОВИ НАЛАЗИ ЗАШТИЋЕНИХ И СТРОГОЗАШТИЋЕНИХ ВРСТА ПОТВРЂУЈУ ЗНАЧАЈ ПОДРУЧЈА ЗНАЧАЈНИХ ЗА ОПСТАНАК ОСОЛИКИХ МУВА (РНА)

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РЕЗИМЕ: С порастом антропогеног притиска на животну средину, успоста-вљање заштићених подручја једна је од најзначајних стратегија за очување биодиверзитета. Чињеница да многе врсте губе битку са изумирањем, без обзира на то што се налазе у оквиру заштићених подручја, потеже се питање њихове евалуације. Циљ ове студије је процена Подручја значајних за опстанак осоликих мува (РНА) и подручја која то још нису, а потенцијално би могла бити у будућности, користећи податке из нових теренских истраживања. За ову сврху је искоришћен Т-тест. Поред тога, модели потенцијалне дистрибуције врста креирани су за две нове врсте које су препознате као значајне и додате на списак кључних врста. Креиране мапе су преклопљене с мапама заштићених подручја и РНА подручја како би се уочио проценат преклапања. Резултати Т-теста нису статистички значајни, али би то могла бити последица других фактора, као што је мала величина узорка. С друге стране, резултати моделовања потенцијалне дистрибуције врста и преклапања мапа би се могли тумачити као додатна потврда значаја РНА мреже.

КЉУЧНЕ РЕЧИ: осолике муве, Подручја значајна за опстанак осоликих мува, евалуација, конзервација